

TENDENCIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES AND PSYCHOLOGISTS

Kilicheva Karamat

Professor and Doctor of Science, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

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Abstract. *Self-development and self-expression of each pedagogue is directly related to his creativity. Usually, the ability of pedagogues to be creative is ensured by striving to solve pedagogical problems, carrying out scientific research or scientific projects, and achieving mutual creative cooperation. A teacher does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed by consistent study and work on himself over a period of time, and it gradually improves and develops. Therefore, the objective of this paper is to analyze some of the pioneering theories and educational trends on creativity and their usage in pedagogy and psychology to improve creative competence.*

Keywords: *creativity, psychology of creativity, Paul Torrance, development of creative thinking skills.*

Annotatsiya. *Har bir pedagogning o'z-o'zini rivojlantirishi, o'zini namoyon qilishi bevosita uning kreativligiga bog'liqdir. Odatda pedagoglarning kreativlik qobiliyati pedagogik muammolarni hal qilishga intilish, ilmiy tadqiqot yoki ilmiy loyihalarni amalga oshirish, o'zaro ijodiy hamkorlikka erishish orqali ta'minlanadi. O'qituvchi o'z-o'zidan ijodkorga aylanmaydi. Uning kreativ qobiliyati ma'lum vaqt davomida izchil o'rganish va o'z ustida ishlash orqali shakllanadi va u asta-sekin takomillashib, rivojlanib boradi. Shu sababli, ushbu maqolaning maqsadi kreativlik bo'yicha ba'zi ilg'or nazariyalar va ta'lim yo'nalishlarini tahlil qilish va ulardan pedagogika va psixologiyada ijodiy kompetentsiyani yaxshilash uchun foydalanishdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kreativlik, kreativlik psixologiyasi, Pol Torrens, kreativ fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish.*

Аннотация. *Саморазвитие и самовыражение каждого педагога напрямую связано с его творчеством. Обычно способность педагогов к творчеству обеспечивается стремлением к решению педагогических задач, проведением научных исследований или научных проектов, достижением взаимного творческого сотрудничества. Учитель не становится творцом сам по себе. Его творческие способности формируются путем последовательного обучения и работы над собой на протяжении определенного периода времени и постепенно совершенствуются и развиваются. Поэтому целью данной статьи является анализ некоторых новаторских теорий и образовательных тенденций творчества, а также их использования в педагогике и психологии для улучшения творческой компетентности.*

Ключевые слова: *креативность, психология креативности, Пол Торренс, развитие навыков креативного мышления.*

Introduction

The development of practical pedagogy and psychology in conditions of rapid social change and reform of the education system requires the training of pedagogues and psychologists who are able to creatively solve issues that arise in professional activities. However, the continuing academic nature of the training of educators and psychologists does not fully ensure the

development of students' creative abilities. As a result, university graduates, having a sufficient amount of special knowledge, professional skills, freedom in choosing forms and methods of work, experience difficulties in making and executing operational decisions in non-standard situations.

In recent decades, innovation in teaching and upbringing has attracted the attention of not only teachers, but also sociologists, philosophers, and psychologists. The most significant feature of the current situation in the education system is the coexistence of two strategies for organizing education: traditional and innovative. Innovative learning is interpreted as focused on creating the individual's readiness for rapidly advancing changes in society, readiness for an uncertain future through the development of creativity, diverse forms of thinking, as well as the ability to cooperate with other people. The main features of innovative learning are “anticipation” and “participation”. Innovative learning as a strategy for mass education brings a deeper change in education. As an analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature on the problem under consideration shows, the end of the 20th century is a period of “global innovation” in all areas of culture, economics, technology, social and individual life.

Global innovation processes are accompanied by an acceleration in the development of all aspects of social life, which aggravates and deepens the contradiction between the pace of social and individual socio-cultural development. Considering the functions of the modern education system on the scale of these changes, one should associate the possibilities of overcoming the contradiction with two alternative strategies for organizing education. Innovative teaching creates a new type of educational process that liberates the personality of the teacher and student.

Psychology of creativity

Creativity is the ability to generate new ideas, find innovative solutions, and see worlds of possibilities. It is a process that involves a combination of intuition, associative thinking and the ability to see connections between different elements. Creativity is an important part of human nature and can be developed through certain strategies and techniques.

Ellis Paul Torrance, who is also known as “father of creativity”, devoted his career to teaching and researching creativity. His interest in creativity emerged in 1937 from his observation that many his difficult student went on to become successful in life and work. During his working for the U.S. Air Force (1951-57), he developed his survival definition of creativity, which stated that a courageous risk-taking is essential for creativity. Later he defines creativity as “...the process of sensing gaps or disturbing, missing elements; forming ideas or hypotheses concerning them; testing these hypotheses; and communicating the results, possibly modifying and retesting the hypotheses.” *Torrance with his colleagues* invented the most widely known, The Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking, which was published in 1966. He developed a benchmark method for quantifying creativity. At the beginning he used use Guilford's (1956) four divergent thinking factors:

- 1) Fluency. The total number of interpretable, meaningful, and relevant ideas generated in response to the stimulus.
- 2) Flexibility. the number of different categories or shifts in responses.
- 3) Originality. the number of unusual yet relevant ideas and the statistical rarity of the responses.
- 4) Elaboration. The amount of detail used to extend a response

For people with a creative level, an empirically discovered pattern becomes not the end point of the thinking process, but an independent goal of further research. This is what is recognized as the most important factor in creativity and is established in numerous tests of

sensitivity to problems. Having discovered a pattern, a person with a creative level of intellectual activity asks himself non-practical questions: “What is behind this?” and moves further, bringing the “scooping out” of the object of knowledge to the creation of a theory that explains the nature of the facts. A person with a creative type of intellectual activity turns out to be more resistant to the influence of external conditions. Teachers' focus on external assessment of performance is usually a clear indicator of their commitment to external influences.

Thus, creativity develops in the process of assimilation of what has already been accumulated, and then a change and transformation of the teacher's existing experience is carried out. This is the path from adaptation to pedagogical innovation to its transformation, which constitutes the essence and dynamics of the teacher's innovative activity. In this regard, the issue of the relationship between skill and creativity in the professional activities of a teacher should be considered. Mass pedagogical experience is a typical experience of an educational institution, which characterizes the achieved level of practice in teaching, upbringing and the implementation of the achievements of pedagogical science in it.

Creativity is a skill that can be developed. To do this, regularly practice various methods of stimulating creative thinking. Practice generating ideas, participate in creative projects, experiment with different ways of solving problems. It must be taken into account that developing creativity is an ongoing process that requires openness to new ideas and a willingness to think outside the box.

Conclusion

Creativity can be found in every area of life, from the way you decorate your residence to a new way of understanding how a cell works. Creativity is a complex subject and researchers are still working to understand exactly what factors contribute to the ability to think creatively. While some people seem to come by creativity naturally, there are also things you can do to build and strengthen this ability.

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